

MUSIC CULTURE LESSONS USING MODERN METHODS OF USING THE SONGS OF THE FIRST UZBEK COMPOSERS

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Annotation: Didactic games and how to use them are given in these music culture classes. Instructions are given on which works should be used more to educate students in the national spirit.

Keywords: Music pedagogy, upbringing, education, information, development, knowledge, skills, competence, pedagogical skills, didactics

Annotatsiya: Mazkur musiqa madaniyati darslarida didaktiv o'yinlar, ulardan qanday tarzda foydalanishlar to'g'risida ma'lumotlar berilgan. O'quvchilarni milliy ruhda tarbiyalashda qaysi asarlardan ko'proq foydalanishlar haqida ko'rsatmalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Musiqa pedagogikasi, tarbiya, ta'lim, ma'lumot, rivojlanish, bilim, ko'nikma, malaka, pedagogik mahorat, didaktika.

Аннотация: На занятиях по музыкальной культуре даются дидактические игры и способы их использования, даются указания, какие произведения следует больше использовать для воспитания учащихся в национальном духе.

Ключевые слова: Музыкальная педагогика, воспитание, образование, информация, развитие, знания, умения, компетентность, педагогическое мастерство, дидактика.

It is no exaggeration to say that music is one of the most favorite subjects for children among the classes held in primary grades at school. Each of us, based on our own life experience, if we think about our childhood times for a moment, we are sure that our childhood times were the most beautiful moments of our life. We will be This is because in childhood we learned to enjoy every moment of life. The flying of butterflies, the singing of birds, the beautifully drawn color picture on the cover of our book, the melody and melody emanating from the sound of some musical instrument did not leave our hearts indifferent. Through observations, I was convinced that the education given during childhood determines what kind of person a child will be in the future has a great influence on its development.[1] Music, visual arts, children who love nature, literature, and what kind of careers they will have in the future no matter what, he has a delicate taste, good manners, order and discipline, one in other words, possessing qualities that adorn people.

I was a witness of their achievements. In the five important initiatives put forward by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev at the meeting on March 19, 2019 in order to increase attention to the education of young people, they were promoted in culture, art, literature, wide involvement in physical education and sports, from information technologies formation of effective use skills and reading to the issues of wide promotion and employment of women and girls.[2]

It is important that they paid special attention from the point of view, organization of music culture classes in secondary schools in more interesting non-traditional forms is one of the most urgent issues of today.

It can be noted that it is a city and district in Namangan region elementary school music lessons are still unprofessional in their schools by personnel, more precisely by primary school teachers it's just being used in name only. Mostly music culture lessons the fact that it is being held as a continuation of mathematics, reading, mother tongue classes it's sad. If analyzed, the lessons of music culture are mainly includes the following activities.

These include:

1. Music literacy.
2. Listening to music.
3. Sing as a group
4. Rhythmic accompaniment to music.
5. Performance of children's musical instruments.[3]

Annual work plan of general music culture activities is determined in advance by the music designers. School music educators take classes without deviating from this set plan they will have to go. The plan includes every quarter and study the general theme of the year is determined. The musical literacy part of music lessons is one for children seems a lot more boring. That is why it is possible in this part of the lesson it is necessary to use the demonstration method. For example: stretches of sounds, notes in a line from more colorful pictures to explain the location to children, the effective use of drawings and rebuses facilitates the acquisition of musical literacy. Having a picture of an insect or an object next to each note keeps the exercise from being monotonous and boring. So, in the musical literacy part of the lesson, we will have to focus on demonstration. The music listening part of the music lesson is also for the children it is correct to say that it does not attract too much attention. [4] Usually to listen to music in the annual plan, set the works in advance will be placed. This is one of the famous scholars of the Islamic world Imam Abu

Khamid al-Ghazali's teachings on learning it is permissible to quote. "Learning is of two kinds; the first one learning, and the other learning by discovery". So, organize classes based on strict standards and patterns it is not always the right thing to do. My suggestion is training in the music listening section, it is performed primarily in the tunes of national instruments letting the children hear the tunes, slowly playing dutor, tanbur, rubob, flute, to teach to distinguish the sounds of words such as gijjak

it will be right. In the process of listening to music, the words of the instrument to the children it will be necessary to demonstrate. Let's not forget that music from the very beginning of the training, the children rush to sing faster. Of course, voice warm-up exercises are performed first. Sound warm-up the purpose of the exercises is only to prepare the voice for singing we should not do it. Familiar to children, easy to sing. When we do that we will adjust the sound in one way, and children's love for folk songs we form the feelings of love. If we focus on the group singing part of the lesson, the most favorite and enjoyable part for children is music singing. In order for the piece to be sung to be pleasing to the students, the lower memorable, more fifths. It is made up of melody jumps with a quarter interval, and the words are melodious.[5] It is desirable that it is understandable and fluent. In other cases, the teacher it is very difficult for children to absorb the work. Such a situation every experienced music teacher is prepared for this to teach children one of the prepared works immediately it is necessary to start. This is where the founders of Uzbek children's singing are considered a number of composers: Fattokh Nazarov, Ilyas Akbarov, Mardon Nasimov, Ghafur Kadyrov, Sabir Boboev, Karim Abdullaev, Sonya Abramova, Manas one created by Leviev, Mutal Burkhanov, Shermat Yormatov one of the wonderful songs that will last a lifetime, varied in content and color it is the same term as taking it for singing. I have been offering this for many years. Based on my work experience, I tested it in practice myself, I recommend it to young music educators as a method.

By the talented composers mentioned above even though it was created sixty or seventy years ago among works that have not lost their artistic and educational value we can cite the following children's songs as an example. Makhmudjon Dadaboev Uzbekistan composers as a member of the association, as an academician of "Turon" Academy his songs and poems are printed in elementary school textbooks. We are happy that it came out. From the works of the composers named above.

Another important positive aspect of using it in training is that our master composers are well aware of the masterpieces of our Uzbek national music, so the spirit of our national music is clearly felt in the works they create. Many of their songs contain melodies of folk music. That is why we can say that these works have not lost their charm. [6] As a proof of our words, we would like to present some of the songs of our composers with a musical analysis. This song created by composer Mardon Nasimov has been included in school music textbooks several times. The song is written in 6/8 measure, in the key of D minor, and the range is very convenient for children to sing. The lyrics are understandable and memorable for students. In the work, the nightingale, a wonderful wandering bird of nature, is praised. This is the only way to achieve spiritual maturity and a rich cultural and spiritual heritage.[8]

Before teaching the song to the children, the teacher should talk about this wonderful bird and in the process of teaching the song to the children, he should form feelings of love and affection for mother nature and the world of animals and birds that have taken refuge in her bosom. The second piece, one of the founders of Uzbek children's singing.

In this song, created by the composer Ghafur Kadirov, the work of mothers, their creativity, which is loved by everyone, is praised in pleasant tones. Through this topic, the music teacher should give students an understanding of the incomparable efforts of mothers, their sacrifices from the birth of each person to their maturity. [7] If necessary, in order to further strengthen the subject being taught, the educator can tell the children stories, fairy tales, stories that are close in content to this topic.

In conclusion, we can say that making music culture lessons interesting, focusing on the content rather than the structure, that is, the form of the lessons, is the main factor in achieving the intended goal.

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